

Comparison of Rocuronium with Succinylcholine for Elective Intubation in ENT surgeries

Siva S^{*1}, Vijay Kanna Marappan², Alagu A³

1.Post Graduate,Department of Anesthesiology,Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and
Research Centre

2.Professor, Department of Anesthesiology,Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research
Centre

3.Assistant Professor, Department of Anesthesiology,TrichySRM Medical College Hospital and
Research Centre

*Corresponding Author : Siva S

Abstract

Background: It would be crucial to ascertain which of drugs , especially Rocuronium or succinylcholine, have a low rate of postoperative throat difficulties. The information about intubating conditions could be helpful in selecting a muscle relaxant in a real-world clinical setting, particularly when it comes to elective ENT surgical cases.

Methods: This comparative study was conducted among cases posted for elective ENT surgeries in Trichy SRM Medical college & Research Institute, Trichy. A total of 140 cases were included with 70 cases in group 1 (Succinylcholine) and another 70 cases in group II (Rocuronium). Grades of intubation conditions were used. Data was entered in MS excel and analysed using SPSS. Chi square test was used to assess the association between groups.

Results: In this study both group I and group II were similar in terms of age, gender and ASA classification without any significant association. On assessing the grades of incubating condition of laryngoscope, vocal cord position and reaction to insertion of ET tube and cuff inflation, there were significant associations noted between group I and group II. Clinical duration of action was similar in both the groups with no significant difference in the mean duration of action.

Conclusion: We infer that Rocuronium is comparatively better efficacious in terms of providing excellent intubation condition in terms of laryngoscope, vocal cord position and reaction to insertion of ET tube and cuff inflation. Thus Rocuronium can be a better alternative of succinylcholine among cases undergoing ENT elective surgeries.

Key words: Rocuronium, succinylcholine, Grades of intubation conditions

INTRODUCTION

Common postoperative throat consequences of general anesthesia with tracheal intubation include painful throat and hoarseness, with reported incidences of sore throat ranging from 11 to 48% and hoarseness from 18 to 53%^{1,2}. These adverse effects have an adverse effect on the patient's satisfaction and recuperation and are an unsatisfactory postoperative outcome^{1,3}. Mucosal dehydration, trauma from tracheal intubation, and mucosal erosion from the tracheal tube's cuff are all considered potential causes of postoperative throat problems^{4,5}. Modern anesthesia techniques and enhanced airway devices have significantly decreased these consequences over the past few decades. However, it is unknown if the type of induction agent used during anesthesia can alter the incidence of postoperative throat problems.

One crucial step in rapid sequence induction and intubation (RSII) is the injection of a fast-acting neuromuscular blocking agent (NMBA)⁶. Succinylcholine has historically been the most often used NMBA for RSII because of its rapid onset and good intubation circumstances. Nevertheless, succinylcholine is contraindicated in many circumstances and has major adverse effects⁷. Rocuronium has emerged as a nondepolarizing muscle relaxant substitute for succinylcholine, which has a quicker beginning of action.

According to reports, succinylcholine induction, particularly when administered as a single injection, is linked to a significant prevalence of postoperative sore throat^{8,9}. But in this earlier research, thiopental is used to induce anesthesia along with fentanyl and a muscle relaxant. Therefore, when succinylcholine is added to contemporary short-acting medications like propofol and remifentanyl, its impact on the frequency of postoperative throat problems remains unknown. However, there hasn't been enough research done on the prevalence of rocuronium-related postoperative throat problems. Therefore, it would be crucial to ascertain which of them has a low rate of postoperative throat difficulties. This information could be helpful in selecting a muscle relaxant in a real-world clinical setting, particularly when it comes to elective ENT surgical cases.

METHODS

This comparative study was conducted among cases posted for elective ENT surgeries in Trichy SRM Medical college & Research Institute, Trichy. A total of 140 cases were included with 70

cases in group 1 (Succinylcholine) and another 70 cases in group II (Rocuronium). Cases with age 18-60 and ASA class of 1 and 2 were included. Cases with anticipated difficult airway, MMP class 3 and 4, pregnancy and presence of neuromuscular diseases were excluded.

A thorough pre-anaesthetic evaluation was done a day before surgery and all the necessary investigations were done to rule out any systemic disease. Tab.alprazolam 0.5 mg and Tab. Pantoprazole 40 mg was administered to all patients on the night before surgery. Patients were maintained nil per oral for a duration of 8 hours prior to surgery. On the day of surgery, after the patient is shifted to the operating room, an intravenous line was secured with an appropriately sized intravenous cannula and the patient was connected to a multi-channel monitor.

The baseline heart rate, oxygen saturation and electrocardiogram, systolic, diastolic, mean arterial blood pressure will be recorded. IV Glycopyrrolate 0.2 mg and IV midazolam 1 mg was given to all patients 20-30 minutes prior to administering the induction agent. All patients were preoxygenated with 100% oxygen via a hudson face mask for 3 minutes. One minute after Preoxygenation, IV Fentanyl 1-2 microgram/kg body wt, were given intravenously. They were induced with IV Propofol 2mg/kg body wt.

In group I, Succinylcholine chloride 1.5 mg kg body weight was given intravenously after the loss of verbal response following induction. Similarly in group II Rocuronium bromide 1.2 mg/kg body wt was given intravenously after the loss of verbal response following induction. No mask ventilation was done in any patient after administration of muscle relaxant. In the two groups of patients, oral endotracheal intubation was attempted at 60 seconds following the administration of muscle relaxant and intubating conditions were assessed according to the following criteria.

Assessment of intubating conditions was done as follows:

Laryngoscopy -Easy: Jaw relaxed, no resistance to blade insertion; Fair: Jaw not fully relaxed, slight resistance to blade insertion; Difficult: Poor jaw relaxation, active resistance of the patient to laryngoscopy.

Vocal cord position – Abducted; Intermediate / moving; Closed

Reaction to insertion of tracheal tube and cuff inflation - None; Slight (1 or 2 weak contractions / movement lasting < 5 seconds); Vigorous / sustained (> 2 contractions or diaphragmatic movement for > 5 seconds).

Overall intubating conditions were then classified as Excellent, Good and Poor accordingly.

Data was entered in MS excel and analysed using SPSS. Chi square test was used to assess the association between groups.

RESULTS

In this study both group I and group II were similar in terms of age, gender and ASA classification without any significant association.

Table 1: Clinical profile of study participants

Variables	Group I	Group II	p value
Age group			
18-30 years	21	24	0.6358
31-40 years	24	28	
41-50 years	16	12	
51-60 years	9	6	
Total	70	70	
Gender			
Male	43	39	0.7359
Female	27	31	
Total	70	70	
ASA classification			
Class 1	32	28	0.7152
Class 2	38	42	
Total	70	70	

On assessing the grades of incubating condition of laryngoscope, there was a significant association noted between group I and group II.

Table 2: Grades of incubating condition - laryngoscope

Laryngoscope	Group I	Group II	p value
Excellent	45	61	0.0053*
Good	19	8	
Poor	6	1	
Total	70	70	

*Significant

On assessing the grades of incubating conditions of vocal cord position, there was a significant association noted between group I and group II.

Table 3: Grades of incubating condition - Vocal Cord Position

Vocal Cord Position	Group I	Group II	p value
Excellent	42	57	0.0119*
Good	19	11	
Poor	9	2	
Total	70	70	

*Significant

On assessing the grades of incubating condition of reaction to insertion of ET tube and cuff inflation, there was a significant association noted between group I and group II.

Table 4: Grades of incubating condition - Reaction to insertion of ET tube and cuff inflation

Reaction to insertion of ET tube and cuff inflation	Group I	Group II	p value
Excellent	41	62	0.0002*
Good	20	7	
Poor	9	1	
Total	70	70	

*Significant

Clinical duration of action was similar in both the groups with no significant difference in the mean duration of action.

DISCUSSION

For quick sequence induction and intubation, Wang J et al¹⁰ evaluated the incidence of postoperative sore throat, hoarseness, and myalgia between rocuronium and succinylcholine. 90% of patients in group R and 6.7% of patients in group S, respectively, had excellent and good intubating circumstances. These statistics were comparable. In the PACU, group Swa's incidence of postoperative sore throat was considerably higher than group R's at 12 and 24 hours after surgery; however, these differences became negligible at 48 hours. At each time point, there were a few cases of hoarseness and/or myalgia in both groups, but the differences were not statistically significant. Thus compared with rocuronium, succinylcholine administration was related with high prevalence of postoperative sore throat. Perry JJ et al¹¹ investigated whether succinylcholine-induced intubation circumstances during RSII are comparable to those produced by rocuronium. Out of the forty articles found, ten were deemed ineligible based on the inclusion criteria, two were published twice, and two lacked adequate information. As a result, 26 studies were examined. In general, rocuronium performed worse than succinylcholine (RR = 0.87). With a relative risk of 0.96, the intubation conditions in the propofol subgroup were comparable. Intubation failure rates were similar across the two groups. Overall, succinylcholine produces superior intubation conditions with a higher degree of consistency than rocuronium. When

combined with propofol, rocuronium produces intubation conditions comparable to those of succinylcholine, should a second-line drug be necessary. The speed at which spontaneous breathing could resume following RSII was evaluated by Sørensen MK et al¹². They proposed that rocuronium–sugammadex would result in spontaneous ventilation sooner than succinylcholine in the event of tracheal intubation. Compared to succinylcholine, RSII with rocuronium and sugammadex reversal allowed spontaneous breathing to resume earlier.

According to Tran DT et al¹³, succinylcholine was found to be more effective than rocuronium in terms of achieving both excellent and clinically acceptable intubation circumstances. The quality of evidence was moderate for these conclusions due to a high incidence of detection bias among the trials and significant heterogeneity. When thiopental was used as the induction agent, succinylcholine was more likely to result in excellent intubating conditions (risk ratio 0.81 with or without the use of opioids). The clinically significant distinctions between succinylcholine and rocuronium in securing appropriate intubating circumstances during RSI of anesthesia with propofol were evaluated by Andrews JI et al¹⁴. With succinylcholine and rocuronium, the incidence of clinically acceptable intubating circumstances was 97.1% and 93.2%, respectively, with a 3.9% difference. They asserted that succinylcholine and rocuronium administered together in a RSI of anesthesia is clinically similar.

According to Mallon WK et al¹⁵, there was no statistically significant difference between the two agents' outcomes in terms of clinically appropriate intubation circumstances and time to commencement. Higher satisfaction scores appear to be produced under settings that contain succinylcholine. They highlighted that Succinylcholine remains the medication of choice for ED RSI unless there is a contraindication to its treatment. The noninferiority of rocuronium vs succinylcholine for tracheal intubation in out-of-hospital emergency scenarios was evaluated by Guihard B et al¹⁶. 74.6% of patients in the rocuronium group and 79.4% in the succinylcholine group successfully underwent first-attempt intubation. In patients receiving endotracheal intubation in an emergency situation outside of a hospital, rocuronium did not show a noninferiority in terms of the success rate of the first attempt at intubation when compared to succinylcholine. According to a study by Sluga M et al¹⁷, succinylcholine delivery resulted in a shorter intubation time than rocuronium administration. On a 9-point rating system, the endotracheal intubation circumstances were superior following succinylcholine than following

rocuronium. Between the groups, there was no discernible difference in patients with poor intubation conditions or patients who had a failed initial attempt at intubation. They came to the conclusion that succinylcholine, as opposed to rocuronium, produces better intubation circumstances and permits a quicker endotracheal intubation sequence during the rapid sequence induction of anesthesia in urgent patients.

During rapid sequence induction, Mazurek AJ et al¹⁸ evaluated the onset and quality of muscle paralysis and intubation circumstances using succinylcholine (Sch) or rocuronium (Rot). There was no significant difference in timing of onset of apnea for Sch versus Rot. The restoration of the first twitch response was much faster with Sch compared with Rot. Thiopental and rocuronium gave similar circumstances to thiopenta and succinylcholine, allowing intubation to be completed in less than 60 seconds in pediatric patients scheduled for emergency surgery. They came to the conclusion that when a quick return to spontaneous breathing is not needed, rocuronium is a suitable replacement for succinylcholine in children with RSI.

CONCLUSION

We infer that Rocuronium is comparatively better efficacious in terms of providing excellent intubation condition in terms of laryngoscope, vocal cord position and reaction to insertion of ET tube and cuff inflation. Thus Rocuronium can be a better alternative of succinylcholine among cases undergoing ENT elective surgeries.

Declarations

Funding: No funding source

Conflict of interest: None declared

Ethical approval: This study was registered with the Institutional Human Ethical Committee.

REFERENCES

1. Higgins PP, Chung F, Mezei G: Postoperative sore throat after ambulatory surgery. British journal of anaesthesia 2002, 88(4):582-584 .

2. Tazeh-Kand NF, Eslami B, Mohammadian K: Inhaled fluticasone propionate reduces postoperative sore throat, cough, and hoarseness. *Anesthesia and analgesia* 2010, 111(4):895-898.
3. Inoue S, Abe R, Tanaka Y, Kawaguchi M: Tracheal intubation by trainees does not alter the incidence or duration of postoperative sore throat and hoarseness: a teaching hospital-based propensity score analysis. *British journal of anaesthesia* 2015, 115(3):463-469.
4. Combes X, Schavuliege F, Peyrouset O, Motamed C, Kirov K, Dhonneur G, Duvaldestin P: Intracuff pressure and tracheal morbidity: influence of filling with saline during nitrous oxide anesthesia. *Anesthesiology* 2001, 95(5):1120-1124.
5. Navarro RM, Baughman VL: Lidocaine in the endotracheal tube cuff reduces postoperative sore throat. *Journal of clinical anesthesia* 1997, 9(5):394-397.
6. Jensen AG, Callesen T, Hagemo JS, Hreinsson K, Lund V, Nordmark J, Clinical Practice Committee of the Scandinavian Society of A, Intensive Care M: Scandinavian clinical practice guidelines on general anaesthesia for emergency situations. *Acta anaesthesiologica Scandinavica* 2010, 54(8):922-950.
7. Geldner G, Wulf H: Muscle relaxants suitable for day case surgery. *European journal of anaesthesiology Supplement* 2001, 23:43-46.
8. Capan LM, Bruce DL, Patel KP, Turndorf H: Succinylcholine-induced postoperative sore throat. *Anesthesiology* 1983, 59(3):202-206.
9. Solatpour F, Teymourian H, Mohajerani SA, Hoseinzadegan Shirazi F, Lotfollah Zadeh S, Baikpour M, Amraei R: Comparison of the incidence of sore throat after rapid sequence intubation with succinylcholine and cisatracurium. *Anesthesiology and pain medicine* 2014, 4(3):e20030.
10. Wang J, Du F, Cang J, Liang C, Xue Z. The comparison of the incidence of postoperative Sore Throat, Hoarseness and Myalgia between rocuronium and succinylcholine for RSI: a randomized controlled trial.
11. Perry JJ, Lee J, Wells G. Are intubation conditions using rocuronium equivalent to those using succinylcholine?. *Academic Emergency Medicine*. 2002 Aug;9(8):813-23.
12. Sørensen MK, Bretlau C, Gätke MR, Sørensen AM, Rasmussen LS. Rapid sequence induction and intubation with rocuronium–sugammadex compared with succinylcholine: a randomized trial. *British journal of anaesthesia*. 2012 Apr 1;108(4):682-9.

13. Tran DT, Newton EK, Mount VA, Lee JS, Mansour C, Wells GA, Perry JJ. Rocuronium vs. succinylcholine for rapid sequence intubation: a Cochrane systematic review. *Anaesthesia*. 2017 Jun;72(6):765-77.
14. Andrews JI, Kumar N, Van Den Brom RH, Olkkola KT, Roest GJ, Wright PM. A large simple randomized trial of rocuronium versus succinylcholine in rapid-sequence induction of anaesthesia along with propofol. *Acta anaesthesiologica scandinavica*. 1999 Jan;43(1):4-8.
15. Mallon WK, Keim SM, Shoenberger JM, Walls RM. Rocuronium vs. succinylcholine in the emergency department: a critical appraisal. *The Journal of emergency medicine*. 2009 Aug 1;37(2):183-8.
16. Guihard B, Chollet-Xémard C, Lakhnati P, Vivien B, Broche C, Savary D, Ricard-Hibon A, dit Cassou PJ, Adnet F, Wiel E, Deutsch J. Effect of rocuronium vs succinylcholine on endotracheal intubation success rate among patients undergoing out-of-hospital rapid sequence intubation: a randomized clinical trial. *Jama*. 2019 Dec 17;322(23):2303-12.
17. Sluga M, Ummenhofer W, Studer W, Siegemund M, Marsch SC. Rocuronium versus succinylcholine for rapid sequence induction of anesthesia and endotracheal intubation: a prospective, randomized trial in emergent cases. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*. 2005 Nov 1;101(5):1356-61.
18. Mazurek AJ, Rae B, Hann S, Kim JI, Castro B, Cote CJ. Rocuronium versus succinylcholine: are they equally effective during rapid-sequence induction of anesthesia?. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*. 1998 Dec 1;87(6):1259-62.